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Exploring the Limitations of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Achieving Global Evangelicalism

Hezekiah Adeloye OGUNLOWO

CAC Theological Seminary Igolo Campus FESTAC Route, Igolo Republic of Benin

hezlowo@gmail.com, +2347036114718, +229-96027910, <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4296-0225>

Abstract

Scientific awareness, discoveries, and advancement is now a reality to a common illiterate in villages and urban settlements alike. They might be limited to accessing its products, uses or dividends due to some reasons such as being unable to manipulate it – android illiteracy or rural areas where wifi or internet facilities are limitedly provided but it no one doubts the reality of science anymore especially in banking and commerce sectors where everyone can feel or see the reality of AI. The lacuna this paper attempts to fill is the overwhelming place of prominence the scientific advancement is being given, especially Artificial Intelligence-AI- which is almost usurping God’s ordained relational life and consequent communality. This write up sought to posit that as good as scientific advancement might be especially Artificial Intelligence (AI), it should be guided against lest it erodes relationalism and communality. Literature review, reflections guided by the Bible, participant observations and questionnaire were used as methods to reap from reservoir of knowledge from the society so as to put forward his standpoint. Copies of online questionnaire were given to 120 respondents but 35 copies were filled within 2 weeks. The responses are reported in simple percentage for easy comprehension. It was found out that the opinions gravitate between AI eroding ‘relationalism’ or communality or not. It is recommended that AI is just but one of the many tools provided by science among others for global evangelicalism, and so Artificial Intelligence as good, useful and helpful as it is, it should not take the place of God and man or substitute for expected personal relationship with God, as the order is prescribed in the bible. It is with the objective that the paper assists readers to have a balanced view of science and religion in their inter-relatedness and independences.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Evangelicalism, Relationalism, Transhumanism, Digital Habitus

Introduction

This paper defined the key words in the abstract above. It looked into the history of artificial intelligence in a jiffy, examples of some Artificial intelligence- machines were mentioned and explain how some work. The ontology of human being and evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) was covered in the paper. Some of the benefits of the AI to the Kingdom of God were also examined, and the responses from the respondents were presented and treated. The paper equally looked into the challenges that AI is posing unto the church of Christ and concluded with the recommendation and conclusion.

There are key words, which in the light of clear and firm understanding of the write up are to be defined. Artificial Intelligence (AI) according to Alexandria and Fernando (Researching AI application in evangelical and Pentecostal/charismatic churches: Purity, Bible & Mission As Driving Forces, : 2024 page 2), is being explained as a development of machine, programmed to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. Instead of merely simulating human thought processes, AI relies on computational models and algorithms designed to analyse patter, make predictions and extra valuable insights from fast data. Or the science and engineering of creating systems that can perform tasks that require intelligence across various data, computation and learning. Sheikh et al (2023) claims ‘no general acceptable definition’. Upon various definitions by specified scholars, he concludes that the definition from the AI KLEG provides the necessary freedom of scope. He thus posits their definition as “systems that display intelligent behaviour by analyzing their environment and taking actions-with some degree of autonomy to achieve specific goals” (p. 2). This definition encompasses all the currently recognizable AI applications while allowing for potential changes in what mankind will consider becoming of AI in the future. In another development, Duggai (2024)

expresses that an Artificial Intelligence program is a program that is capable of conceiving and thinking. He streamlines that it is possible to consider anything to be AI once it consists of a program that performs a task that is meant for humans.

Evangelicalism: Evangelicalism is different from what is known as evangelism. The former is about all that involve to making Christian doctrines as expounded in the scripture practiced and practicable, this may involve social, psychological, economical, spiritual outfits to be put in place from biblical point of view. While the latter is about delivering the gospel message so much that the unsaved or unreached are saved or reached for Christ by receiving saving knowledge of Jesus. David Hillborn explains evangelism and evangelicalism this way. Evangelicalism is a noun coined from the adjective 'evangelical'. 'Evangelical' is etymologically rooted in a Greek New Testament meaning –gospel or good news ('*euangelion*' Greek 'eu' good 'angelion' message/news). He said, "gospel people committed to the simple New Testament Christianity and the central tenets of Apostolic faith, rather than later ecclesiastical accretions" (Hillborn: *Evangelical Truth*: p.16-17), in an effort to seeking and maintaining the presentation of authentic teaching once entrusted to the saints (Jude3). John Stott states, "evangelicalism is neither a recent innovation or a deviation from Christian orthodoxy" (evangelical truth). From the above therefore, evangelicalism is put as a system of belief by the evangelicals that puts forth evangelism in all fronts not only in proclaiming but in practices such as: Biblicism, Christocentrism, crucicentrism, conversionism and activism whereby gospel is demonstrated in evangelism and social services (Bebbington: 1989.p 8).

Relationalism: This is coined from relationship. It is about the arts and acts of relating with God vertically (man-God's ward) and horizontally (man-man ward). In this paper the writer states that as good and helpful the AI may be of great benefit to mankind, it cannot and never will replace or substitute for relationalism, that is, relating with God first and relating with man. From the era of Covid-19 it has become more evident that relating with each other: in worship, at social level, at academic platforms, commercial sectors, in communication sectors, in security field of life things have taken new and different dimensions as if man is no more needed except. Man should not jettison relationalism as it is part of the ontological make up of man, as image of God.

Digital habitus, which is defined as "a system of internationalized scheme that generate all thoughts, actions, desires, and perceptions within digital culture" (Romele, 2024, p.118). This is to state the obvious that man is classified and clustered on terms of 'preferences, tendencies, and expected behaviours' by this it is implied that all actions and contents man produces on line' "can be datafied and hence analyzed" (p.121).

Transhumanism: Transhumanism on the other hand is all about, scientific efforts at making science to develop 'brain' machine interface (a project backed up by Elon Musk) through 'Neuralink' a well-intentioned edifice (but potentially clear for its apparent misuse) to avoid ageing and even death by the transmission from carbon-based life embodied in fleshly bags of bones, muscles and neurons into silicon-based existence (or whatever substrate forms future AI) it brains functions by downloading person's memories and thought patterns to a supper intelligence machine enabling that person to exist beyond limitations of their bodies with extraordinary potentials to change how they would relate to other people and the environment (Joustral, 2019).

Cursory Look at the History of Artificial Intelligence

History of Artificial Intelligence (also known as AI) by myth has been mathematically been in existence from ancient Greek and Egyptians. However, its maturation became emergent as from, 1943-1952 (MCA-IV Data Mining³²) in 1943 McCulloch and Walter put forward artificial neurons and this is being referred to as the premier attempt on AI in 1949Donald Hebb advanced this effort by updating its rule of modifying the connection strength between neurons, and this was tagged as 'Hebbian Learning'. Also, in 1950, Alar Turing made 'Computing Machine and Intelligence'. He was an English Mathematician and he pioneered Machine

Learning.’ by 1952- 1956 Allen Newell and Herbert A. Simeon created what is known as ‘Logic Theorist’ which was used to test many of the mathematical theorems and were proved correct and many more theorems were discovered as a result and more theorems were propounded.

Therefore in 1956, John McCarthy an American scientist at Dartmouth conference coined AI as an academic field. By 1956-1974, during this era, Joseph Weizenbaum formed the first ‘chatbot’ in 1966 which was named ELIZA. As at the time under consideration algorithms were developed to solve mathematical problems, and so in 1972 the first ‘humanoid robot’ was built in Japan named WABOT-1. While in 1974-1980, AI another winter season was experienced because there was a dearth of interest in that governments were not ready to finance research on AI 1980 -1987 experienced and enjoyed a boom in the field of AI In 1980 the effort resurfaced with ‘expert system’. As at this period computer is programmed to emulate decision with precision as of a human expert. The success in the field this period was so outstanding that American Association of Artificial Intelligence was held at Stanford University. 1987 -1993 witnessed another winter season of AI and at this time both the investors and the governments were never interested to fund AI research.

Another milestone was recorded in 1995-2011 when there was an emergence of Intelligence agents, in 1997 IBM Deep Blue beats the world champion Gary Kasparow then became the first computer to beat the world chess champion. In 2002 AI got to home in form of Roomba as a vacuum cleaner. The advancement and the development in 2006 registered it that AI came to stay and has never left, its presence is felt almost everywhere. Now it was no longer limited to solving mathematical, academic or scientific problems again but appeared in the business Sectors such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Netflix etc., powered by AI these further gave birth to Deep Learning, Big Data and Artificial General Intelligence. In 2011 the world had IBM Watson. In 2002 Google launched Android Apps which provides information or users. In 2014 Chatbot-Eugene Goostman and in 2018 was ‘Project Debater’ in 2019 came the pandemic which now makes Artificial Intelligence popular almost in all sectors of mans’endeavours. It has cone to stay. However, it cannot and should not do away with relationalism in human bondings: cultures, communality, society and more importantly in religion. This is because relationship produces all of these. This clarion call is imminent as Artificial Intelligence is promising transhumanism in the nearest future.

Now AI has developed to a remarkable level. The concept of Deep learning, big data, and data science are now trending like a boom. Nowadays companies like Google, Facebook, IBM, and Amazon are working with AI and creating amazing devices. The future of Artificial Intelligence is inspiring and will come with high intelligence (MCA-IV Data Mining32_ AI_History_Keerti_Ditix 2 pdf, p. 4).

According to Church of Scotland work on Faith and Technology, it was said that the history of AI begun with Alan Turin in 1950. Alan made Neural Algorithms’ and was confirmed in 2016 when an AI machine known also as Deep mind learning the rule of the ancient Asian board game G.O. AlphaFold2 project followed the system to solving problems in Biology such as predicting the three-dimensional structure of protein from amino acid. “a breakthrough was achieved in 2020 when deep Mind took only a few hours to predict the structure of a given protein” (p. 2). An exercise or task which could take up too a year of laboratory work.” This equally opens up many exciting new directions of research treatment into causes and treatment of disease” (p. 2).

Examples or Types of AI

There are many kinds of A. I machine today that perform as perfect and intelligently like human in almost every sphere of life as at today, such as:

- i) GPT-3(generative pre-trained transformer version -30developed by US company open AI. it has access to almost all of the text found in the internet.
- ii) Another one is Global neural workspace

- iii) The world has also recorded Chatbot otherwise known as ELIZA in 1960 programmed to provide supportive information or reply to whatever client say to the computer. E.g. Taiwan at the evolution of Covid-19 AI is used to support people in quarantine because of covid.
- iv) CBT, this is Cognitive Behavioural Therapies. This started in UK,2020 and it is used to solving especially case of depressions.
- v) The world has also had ML, Machine Learning a subset to AI
- vi) There is also ANNs Artificial Neural Networks it functions as a key component to AI and M.L.
- vii) CNN is another achievement in the corridor of A. I.it implies Convolutional Neural Networks
- viii) We also have, GANs – standing for Generative Adversarial Networks
- ix) LLMs, this implies the large language models (Brown et al:2020)
- x) Wysa- an AI based emotionally intelligent mobile ‘chatbot’ apps aimed at building mental resilience and promoting neural well beings using text-based conversational interface.

These are some of the AI or AI related machine that works or function as intelligent as human, among many others.

The Ontology of Human beings Juxtaposing the Evolution of AI

The main part of the paper is here. It is here because it is considering the prowess and success recorded in the field or science, communications and technology as against what the bible claims or states. To every good thing, there is a bad or evil side of or to it. These advancements are good, welcomed, useful, and needful, make difficult tasks easier to accomplish in a very shortest possible time. However, there is need to sound a note of caution to mankind that forgetting the nature of man as ‘Imago Dei’ is dangerous to the purpose of his existence on the planet here at the detriment of himself not God.

From the foregoing, it is becoming glaring that man will in the nearest future build machine edifices that will be performing what man is expected to do. For example, man in the book of Genesis, was put in the garden of Eden to ‘work’ it and to ‘take care’ of it (Gen2:15). This is a command to work or ‘till’ (abad), Norman Geisler (Christian Ethics, 1995) said the word in Hebrew means to be a slave to or in modern term ‘care for’ or the word ‘keep’ (Shamar) means to watch or to preserve it. So, by the time man now succeed to have transhumanism in the field of AI that means therefore that all that God has intended man to do on the planet earth is bequeathed to science. The paper does not advocate for, neither accepting nor nonuse of scientific and technological appliances but points to:

1. Duty of man being a steward of the planet earth and therefore must not forget that consciousness which no machine can achieve.
2. That church should act as check and balance in her duty to whatever is the achievement in the world and of the world, because he is light and salt of the world. With her presences, the world is not expected to stray.
3. That church as at this time should play her role well because scientific advancement is almost replacing ‘relationalism’ with non-relationalism. Man is created to relate directly with God and with themselves (Mark 12:30-31) but it appears this advancement is gradually robbing man of relationship with each other but it is leaving us with interactions (online, electronically) but keeping us at bay from truest relationship designed by God.

How does man express love if everything is done by machine. Take for instance marriage, parenting and society. Jesus on this said, ‘who do men say I am?’ Man is created in the image of God to relate- first with God, and reflecting such a relationship in his or her relationship with fellow neighbor. Yes! Man uses scientific apparatuses to disseminate gospel or information faster, do something with ease with help of machine, transacts business, and reaches lands in a matter of minutes. But can man really say he or she actually relates or interact? Communality is almost lost. Could this be gravitation toward the eschatological

time? Everything is now online, worship, market, product, marriages, and this outfit is eroding from our sanity and sanctity of life which is embedded in relationalism (such as sociality, cultures and spirituality- man is having the tendency of depending more on science than God the author of man who makes science). AI is good but should not take away from man relating with God and ourselves.

Benefits of AI Enhancing the Growth and Development of God’s Kingdom

The digital habitus can be used to emphasize or reiterate Missions, scripture reading and prayers, holiness, well-being, prosperity and other values which are determined by the Christian (Alexandria and Fernando, 2024, p. 3). In eschatological terms many churches consider AI as a premonition of the end time and have a facilitator of the apocalyptic destruction of humanity before Christ returns. In some academic department like theology and Bible Translation the assistance of this technological feat is incalculable and invaluable, as it helps in Language translation and some codexes, done faster and easier.

Since this is becoming the ‘new normal’, “Pastors or church leaders who are digital natives, should lead flocks of individuals who are found of technology to find our new mission field of unreached digital tribe” (korpi:2003). Church should develop a theology -engaging and participatory which will help members to navigate technological advancement and development without compromising the teaching of the Bible as to who God is, what man is and the purpose of his existence being doxology.

Presentation and Discussion of the Data from the Questionnaire

There were six basic questions and the data is presented accordingly each question was tested from three points of views (agree, disagree and undecided), the questionnaire was posted electronically to discuss these issues:

1. Artificial Intelligence can disrupt and destroy interpersonal relationship among Christians.
2. Reliance on AI devices and appliances can diminish and erode ethical societal values
3. AI can be utilized to promote the evangelical faith in today’s world.
4. Evangelical Christians should utilize and deploy AI to make the world better.
5. Evangelical Christians should utilize and deploy artificial intelligence to reach the world with gospel message.
6. Evangelical churches and Christians should utilize and deploy AI to facilitate social and societal transformation.

Figure 1: Artificial Intelligence can disrupt and destroy interpersonal relationship among Christians

Figure 2: Reliance on AI devices and appliances can diminish and erode ethical societal values

Figure 3: AI can be utilized to promote the evangelical faith in today's world

Figure 4: Evangelical Christians should utilize and deploy AI to make the world better

Figure 5: Evangelical Christians should utilize and deploy artificial intelligence to reach the world with gospel message

Figure 6: Evangelical churches and Christians should utilize and deploy AI to facilitate social and societal transformation

Responses to Question One have Agreed 57.1%, Disagreed 37.1%, Undecided 5.7%. For Question Two: Agreed 80%, Disagreed 14.3%, Undecided 5.7%. For Question Three: Agreed 77.1%, Disagreed 20%, Undecided 2.9%. For Question Four: Agreed 65.7%, Disagreed 31.4%, Undecided 2.9%. For Question Five: Agreed 71.4%, Disagreed 22.9%, Undecided 5.7%. Finally, for Question Six: Agreed 68.6%, Disagreed 20%, Undecided 11.4%.

These imply that 57.1 percent of the respondents agreed that AI can both disrupt and destroy relationship. As 37 percent said that it cannot affect relationship. This is a caution note that as good or as helpful the AI might adversely affect relationship and so it should be guided in their uses not to affect relationship with God and fellow humans. The second findings came with the report of 80 percent agreeing that reliance on AI can and might erode ethical, social values. Fourteen percent disagreed with this while about 6 percent were indecisive. On the Question Three, 77.1 percent did agree that AI can help facilitates Gospel faster and easier as 20 percent disagreed and about 3 percent were indecisive. The corollary significantly runs that AI is a promising factor and tool to promoting gospel to the digital tribe or family or world.

On Question 4, the findings had about 67 percent agreed, and this implies that AI is not only for its deployment on Kingdom of God, it is also usually helpful and useful to make the world better. About 32 percent did disagree on the deployment of AI for the kingdom uses claiming that it significantly has no effect on making the world any better. Now, since we are in the age of AI the church and the Christian community should develop AI system or machine that can be used to disseminate gospel to hostile areas such as Boko haram affected areas. i.e. hostile areas to gospel. It will cost less in terms of life and formidability. Question 5 reported its findings and implies 71.4 percent of respondents that using the trending AI gadget for gospel messages will yield a bumper harvest. At any rate 22.9 percent disagreed. In that A. I might be good to disseminate but cannot meet some emotional needs which can only be provided by relationship. Question 6. Had the discussion that 68.6 percent agreed that societal transformation is easier to accomplish with the use

of AI, 20 percent disagreed with such that it is man himself which can transform society by the use of culture, religion and societal norm not a programmed machine. 11.4% of the respondents were undecided, this could mean that with the use of both, the human society can be societally transformed.

The Challenges of AI on the Church

This section serves as challenges facing the church but is presented in a way of recommending what the church of God can, and should do in a time such as this. Lynch (2013) cautions that human contact which is exemplified in one-to-one encounter is extremely important and irreplaceable in the church missions. He stresses that even Jesus Christ maintained more of person to person contact in his ministry. Jesus actually trained his 12 Apostles via personal contact; none was operating from afar. Lynch insists that dependence on new technologies can strip that from the church missions. In Faith impact Forum: Society, religion and technology AI Opportunity and challenge, it is made known that “among members states in the UN there is widespread support for a ban on killer robots and with the support more than 30 countries, the Secretary General Antonio Guterre, has proposed a new international treaty...stating. ‘machine that have the power and discretion to kill without human interference are politically unacceptable and morally despicable’” (Joustra: 2019, p. 7). Another challenge before the church is that of privacy (information stored in the internet) over profit, could this be love of money bible talks about.

Recently, according to E. Ekeh, I. Ibeh and I. Meludu (personal communication, April, 2024) the Dioceses of Nnewi and Mbamili Anglican Communion in Anambra State, Nigeria, adopted respectively the “vicilook technology” that provides the public with digital information and access of only verified church priests and church branches around the globe. The church therefore has to do something to help the world out of the woes and merits of AI which is trending like it is done above, the Church of Christ can do better.

There is this moral challenge of responsibility. E.g. driverless car which has accident or damaging things are done. When there is drone used to drop nuclear weapons that destroys both old and young, and vegetations alike as against Deut. 20:18 (Geisler: 1995) Who is to be held responsible? Are the manufacturers or the assisting driver in case of car accident, to be held accountable? The church should ethically weigh some technological advancement and talk or make policy or develop her Theology and Doctrine to guide her members on the uses, abuses and misuse of some of the gadgets in a way that will glorify God. The church could go ahead to develop some apps that will help to block some things that may be dangerous to Christianity (such as pornographic materials and the likes) and those that will be of help in advancing the kingdom of God (such as bible games apps, bible puzzles apps among others). The church should learn to use this opportunity wisely within the ambit of a sound theology. Theological institutions will do well to include AI and Church (merits and demerits) in their curriculum.

Conclusion

The AI is a confirmed and welcomed reality in the field of science and is everywhere present though in variant degrees. However, the church should come in to be ‘light and salt’ to guide the world in the make (production) the use (application) and the deployment of scientific advancement lest the world go astray from God’s purpose of the existence of the world and church. Africans and Nigerians in particular should build AI that will promote their rich heritage of communality and relationalism. AI that is of African orientation and that will be for the use of global evangelicalism.

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